

The Experiential Factor in Corporate Architecture and Branding

A Case Study of Apple Brand Stores, Prada Brand Exhibition, and Volkswagen Autostadt

Bhakti Sharma*

* *Department of Interior Design, Buffalo State College, SUNY (State University of New York)
Buffalo, USA, bhaktisharma@yahoo.com*

Abstract: This research studies the role of ‘Corporate Architecture’ as a visual experience provider to the brand’s customers. The marketing field of the brand—the theatrical corporate space—serves as a catalyst to the human experience. The experiences induced by marketing can be categorized into various Strategic Experiential Modules (SEM) – ‘Sense’, ‘Think’, ‘Feel’, ‘Act’, and ‘Relate’ [1]. This study applies Schmitt’s five strategic models of Experiential Marketing to Corporate Architecture. Developing a holistic experience by meshing architecture, branding, and the cultural expression of the corporation is the element of success in today’s consumer driven market. Schmitt’s models are used as a tool to analyze the user experience of the corporate space. The application of Schmitt’s model to architecture provides a platform to study and manage customer experiences of the built corporate space to a tangible scale. A study of US based Apple’s *brand stores*, Italian Fashion label Prada’s *brand exhibition*, and German Auto Manufacturer Volkswagen’s Autostadt *brand city* forms the basis of the application of Schmitt’s model to architecture. While the Apple stores, designed around the life experience of the users, are examples of ‘Sense’, ‘Thank’, and ‘Act’; the Prada exhibition uses art and architecture as the cultural statement for the brand to create an experience using ‘Think’, and ‘Act’ strategies; the Volkswagen brand city creates a holistic unifying communion experience applying the ‘Relate’ strategy. The research studies the role of Experiential Marketing and Corporate Architecture in creating memorable experiences for its’ users.

Key words: *Corporate Architecture, Experience, Branding*

1. Introduction

“Experiences are events that engage individuals in a personal way.” [2]

“Spatial images are the dreams of society. Wherever the hieroglyphics of any spatial image are deciphered, there the basis of social reality presents itself.” [3]

Space fills the experiential voids in the users lives. Architecture also provides a shared experience for its users. The Standardized Mass Produced Economy and consequently, the Built Space have come a long way since the Industrial Revolution. As Klingmann states, the key focus of architecture has shifted from “one size fits all” to

“customization-for-all” economy in today’s market [4], a term that Pine and Gilmore refer to as ‘Experience Economy’ [2]. In their book, *The Experience Economy: Work is Theatre and Every Business a Stage*, Pine and Gilmore argue, that businesses must orchestrate events that prompt memories for its users. If Companies are the ‘experience stagers’, spaces where companies sell their products become more than venues for doing business—these spaces become the ‘stage’ [2].

The creation of a unique, live, and theatrical brand experience engages its’ users at an interactive level, one that involves a two-way communication within the brand and the target audience. The methodology of engaging target audiences through communication is termed as ‘experiential marketing’. According to Smilansky, the experiential marketing era focuses on giving target audiences a fabulous brand-relevant customer experience that adds value to their lives, and ultimately makes the consumer remember the brand’s marketing –not because it shouted the loudest, but because it gave them an unforgettable experience [5]. In his book, *Experiential Marketing*, Schmitt provides framework for managing these customer experiences. According to him, experiences can be categorized into various Strategic Experiential Modules or SEM’s. Each SEM has a unique structure and principle and ‘experience providers’ or ExPros create SEM’s [1].

This research studies the experiential dimension of space that stimulates emotions in its users using Schmitt’s model as a metaphor for the research. The use of Schmitt’s predictive tool helps in dividing various customer experiences of the brand space into tangible units. It also is instrumental in typifying various corporate architecture market trends. Klingmann emphasizes the need for detail to the transformative dimension of space and the emotions created by its use when applying Schmitt’s model to architecture. She adds that if architecture is a business produced under economic conditions very similar to the ones governing much of mass culture, then the principles of branding, when applied to architecture, entail the expansion of architecture’s potential as a strategic tool in today’s competitive marketplace [4].

The research applies Schmitt’s model of Experiential Marketing to corporate architecture to study the spaces that prompt memories and experiences for its users.

2. Corporate Architecture and Branding

2.1. Converging Phenomenon

The three converging phenomenon that are signaling a need for a corporate architecture that stands apart from its counterparts are – Brand Omnipresence, Customer Retention and Loyalty, and Brand Reverence.

In a world, where brands are ubiquitous and users have an ever-evolving awareness of the brands, it is imperative for the companies to have a strong spatial presence, one that is clearly distinguishable from the established visual identity. Advertising, Names, Logos, Signage, Magalogs, Annual Reports, Product Design and Packaging, Brand Characters, Product Placement, Event Marketing and Sponsorships, Websites and Electronic Media, all serve as Visual Identity Makers for the brand. Retail Stores, Flagship Stores, Brand Exhibitions, Brand Cities on the other hand serve as Spatial Unifiers of the Brand identity. The experience that is created through a stronger visual space where the primary function is to connect with the user distinguishes one brand from the other and makes it unique from visual identity. The corporate or retail space, an experiential environment, is the most comprehensive expression of brand culture [6].

Enhanced customer awareness of the competition also creates a stronger need for retention and loyalty. While in the past, corporations have been successful on user-centered models –consumer benefits, perks, reward points,

customer satisfaction, a need for a stronger two-way communication between the companies and users persists. The need for brand loyalty and consumer appreciation is forcing corporations to use a stronger medium of communication, one that is easily identifiable, to build long lasting brand relationships. Art and Architecture can be said to have been the first mediums of communication, even before the printing press. “Architecture is supposed to shape 'corporate identity', which is also expressed in company logos, websites and merchandise. Nothing is excluded from this policy. Each brand needs its own, easily identifiable architecture with distinctive colours, materials and profile” [7].

Corporate Architecture acts as an experiential catalyst for a spiritual connection between the brand and the consumer. The spatial products of corporate architecture act as pilgrimages for the customers indulging in brand reverence. So much so that ‘Et In Arcadia Ego’ maybe metaphorically applied to Corporate Architecture to reflect that the consumer too once enjoyed the pleasures of the brand monument.

3. Strategic Experiential Modules

According to Schmitt’s Experiential Framework, the five types of marketing that form customer experiences are ‘Sense’, ‘Think’, ‘Feel’, ‘Act’, and ‘Relate’. ‘Sense’ marketing creates sensory experiences in its users; ‘Feel’ Marketing appeals to the customer’s inner feelings; ‘Think’ Marketing utilizes a directional and associative approach to create cognitive and problem solving experiences; ‘Act’ Marketing enhances physical experience and lifestyle changes; and ‘Relate’ Marketing connects the individuals to their ideal self, other people, or cultures [1].

3.1. ‘Sense’

“Sense marketing appeals to the senses with the objective of creating sensory experience through sight, touch, taste, and smell” [1]. Schmitt identifies sense as the differentiator, as a motivator, and as a value provider. When sense campaigns are executed in an unusual and special manner, they act as differentiators. An example is James Turrell’s installation of the Skyscape. The installation of a shaded canopy serves as a frame for the sky heightens the users awareness of the sky and light. The emptiness of the space is overcome by the sensory response of the users. Sense campaigns may also provide an optimal level of stimulation and activation motivating the customers to try new products and eventually buy them.

3.2. ‘Think’

According to Schmitt, the objective of ‘Think’ is to encourage customers to engage in elaborative and creative thinking that may result in the reevaluation of the company and products [1].

Klingmann quotes ‘Think’ appeals to engage customers’ convergent and divergent thinking through surprise, intrigue and provocation [4]. An example that comes to mind is Future Systems’ iconic department store for Selfridges in Birmingham, a metaphorical representation of a Paco Rabanne dress. The shell of the building acts as a mirror to weather, daylight conditions, people, objects, thereby creating a live and animate form. The architects have “re-interpreted the notion of a department store, not just in its form and appearance but also in the social function such a building now plays in our society” [8].

3.3. ‘Feel’

“‘Feel’ appeals to customers’ inner feelings and emotions, with the objective of creating affective experiences” [1].

These affective experiences can range in the emotional involvement of the user. Giuseppe Mengoni’s world’s

oldest shopping arcade, the Galleria Vittorio Emanuele in Milan invokes a feeling of richness and luxury, illusively empowering its' patrons to spend more.

3.4. 'Act'

True to its' name, 'Act' campaigns are aimed at enriching customer lifestyles by showing them alternative ways of doing things.

An example of Act Architecture is the Piano Staircase at the Stockholm's Odenplan subway station that converts users footsteps into music, thereby increasing the people who use the stairs over escalator by 66%.

3.5. 'Relate'

'Relate' campaigns appeal to individual's personal needs, but one that creates a wider social reaction [1]. The 'Relate' campaigns connect the single person to a broader social system.

Klingmann points out the power of icons – the Big Ben in London, the Eiffel Tower in Paris, the Twin Towers in New York City – to reflect a social system [4].

Table 1. Analysis of Schmitt's Model

SEM	Facilitator of	Triggers
'SENSE'	Sensory experiences in users	Sight, Touch, Taste, Smell
'THINK'	Elaborative customer thinking	Surprise, Intrigue, Provocation
'FEEL'	Creating effective experiences	Inner feelings and emotions
'ACT'	Enriching customer lifestyle	Alternate ways of doing things
'RELATE'	Creating wider social reactions	Personal Needs

4. Applying Strategic Experiential Modules to Examples of Corporate Architecture

4.1 Apple Brand Stores

Apple is a US based multinational company known best for its' comprehensive aesthetic design. When Ron Johnson, the Senior Vice President of Retail at Apple announced in a press conference in April 2004, that by entering the retail sector, Apple wished to change the way people shopped, Apple was received with mixed reactions [9]. But since its entry into the retail market, Apple stores have developed an iconic presence in the urban landscape.

Along with the intention of reinforcing the brand image, Johnson states that, the Apple Stores operate with the objectives of a) creating the life experience of the users in the store and b) creating an ownership experience for the customers. The 'destination centers' located in major metropolitan areas and urban retail centers create a strong visual presence for Apple.

The Apple brand stores and high-profile stores are experience providers for its users. Approaching the Apple stores from Schmitt's model, the stores fit into various experiential modules.

4.1.1 Apple and 'Sense'

Apple stores provide an opportunity for consumers to have an up-close and tactile encounter with products in a simple yet sophisticated environment [10]. The store layout, arranged around interests, allows for customers to touch, feel, hear, and sense the gadgets of their choice and preference. The 'solution zones' as they are called are managed by 'geniuses', dressed in blue, orange, or black depending on their area of service or solution.

Besides sales, the key motive of the stores is to dispense advice to its' customers [11]. A serene yet simple environment with careful attention to detail, the Apple stores stimulate the senses to absorb more information about the product. The serene environment is not only achieved by reduced materiality, but also by thoughtfully

integrating building systems, simple yet detailed furniture pieces, and by hiding otherwise distracting architectural elements like sprinkler heads, cameras etc.

4.1.2 Apple and ‘Think’

Apple’s transparent storefront systems attract the customers through surprise, intrigue, and provocation. As Backus discusses, “the centrally positioned, distinctly axial with the entrance space becomes a place of orientation and a compelling invitation from the street” [10]. The Apple products become the visual magnet that attracts the customers to the store. As the customer walks through the store made of glass, stainless steel, and wood, only a quarter of the store is arranged around the product, the rest is around people’s interests and lives [11].

4.1.3 Apple and ‘Act’

The ‘Act’ Module enhances and alters customer lifestyle by setting new and distinct examples. “The Apple Store is like an underground club that patrons enter to see and be seen, to socialize, to network, and maybe even to purchase products” [12]. Historically, underground retail spaces have been less successful retail spaces. The Fifth Avenue Cube Store that we discuss in detail later is not only an inviting underground retail space, but also a 24X7 activity hub.

4.1.4 The Apple Cube

The Apple Cube on Fifth Avenue New York, designed by the architectural group of Bohlin Cywinski Jackson is an extension of the elegant simplicity of its products and an embodiment of the Corporate Philosophy of Apple. True to its brand philosophy, of ‘doing things to create an impact’ [12], the Cube definitely leaves a strong impression in the consumer’s mind.

The 32-foot cube occupies the street-level plaza and underground concourse of the Edward Durrell Stone's General Motors building. Besides serving as an inviting, monumental entrance to the underground retail space, the glass cube floods the underground space with daylight—an example of sense architecture. Smith compares the geometry of the technically precise, clean, and mysteriously breathtaking Cube with Pei’s Louvre [12].

The user descends to the retail space through a circular glass staircase, one that has received a design patent of its own. The stairs on the convergence of several technologies, including laminated glass production, and a panel construction that's called "point-supported." ‘Glass lift walls form the inner wall of the stair. The external guardrail picks up the outer edge of the treads by custom fittings’ [13]. The glass staircase, the bridge, and the glass cube all transfer the feeling of lightness and transparency to the user. An example of ‘Act’ Architecture, the glass cube and the staircase move the consumer to act and explore the underground retail space. Quoting Johnson, “Anything below-grade is famously difficult as retail space because it depends on luring fickle shoppers away from the street, if we believed that if we get the design right, we can get people to go down” [14].

Once inside the space, the Fifth Avenue Store incorporates the modernist design true to its other stores. A clean and distinct environment allows for its users to feel at ease and away from technical problems. Technical service and diagnostic help are offered at a 45-foot long genius bar. The deletion of extraneous elements can be seen throughout the store. The custom ceiling treatment of concealing the supply and return vents in patterned perforated holes, the placement of light boxes, cameras, in aluminum troughs, and the hidden technical wiring slots under the furniture all are architectural and design elements that create a dramatic yet defined space in the Apple Cube. Apple’s serene environment creates a non-technical space for the users, one that is similar to their life experiences.

Ranging from distinctive to revolutionary, the Apple store experience is staged by products, people, places, one that is based on ‘Sense’, ‘Think’, and ‘Act’ modules of Schmitt’s models.

4.2 Prada Brand Exhibition

Prada is an Italian Label specializing in luxury fashion for men and women. When Prada Marfa, a permanent public sculpture created by artists Michael Elmgreen and Ingar Dragset was installed in West Texas in 2005, the critical association of Prada, Art, and Architecture was not instantly visible. Gallery ownership, contemporary art collecting, and the patronage of "cutting-edge" architectural practices all appeared to contribute to the enhancement of Prada's image and the redefinition of its corporate identity [15].

Started in the late nineties, Prada’s acquisition and expansion policy to make its’ products available to a larger customer base demanded a stronger more unique presence by the brand. Ryan confirms that the unrestrained consolidation and increasing homogeneity of the nineties were factors, which forced luxury fashion houses to develop a unique identity as a means of differentiation within the sector [15].

Along with the intention of developing a unique identity through Art, Architecture, and Cultural Association, Prada Exhibition operates with the objective of brand advert, shrine, and lifestyle representation.

The collaboration between Miuccia Prada, part owner of the brand, Fondazione Prada, the management company for Prada’s art collection, and internationally renowned architect Rem Koolhaas has been instrumental in creating Prada’s unique identity with a strong cultural message. Over the years, Koolhaas’s firm Office for Metropolitan Architecture (OMA) and Prada have created cultural and experiential icons in architecture.

4.2.1 Prada and ‘Think’

According to Schmitt, The essence of ‘Think’ is to appeal to customers’ creative thinking about the company and its brand [1]. ‘Think’ also appeals to engage customer’s convergent and divergent thinking through surprise, intrigue, and provocation. Klingmann points out that OMA’s Prada stores subvert all preconceived notions of familiar building typologies thereby evoking an ephemeral notion [4]. The theatrical staircase ramp reminiscent of stadium seating in the Prada SoHo store transcends its material form to engage the audience in a dialog. The ramp stairs act as a metaphorical catwalk for the customers, thereby becoming a catalyst for perceptual values and transformative experiences. The famous ‘wave’ staircase can be modified to become a staircase at the push of a button, thereby taking the theatrical effect of the space to another level of provocation or as Hart suggests “It's not just shopping, it's theater” [8]

4.2.2 Prada and ‘Act’

Koolhaas argues, “shopping is indeed the last remaining form of public activity” [19]. In the 22000 square feet two level space, retail space has been sacrificed to the creation of the ‘wave’, a space where people are invited to interact or socialize. Muschamp urges his readers to think of the Prada Epicenter in SoHo as a “museum show on indefinite display,” one where the consumers become the art and the actors [20]. By creating cultural retail spaces, Prada is “re-injecting public space into the commercialised desert of Soho” [21], thereby altering consumer lifestyle—Act Architecture.

4.2.3 The Prada Transformer

The Prada Transformer in Seoul, Korea is a pioneering temporary exhibition space that has the flexibility to be transformed into different shapes depending on the event. The building is composed of four entirely different structures housed inside the same tetrahedron shape. With the help of four cranes, the structure changes into four

distinct shapes: a hexagon, a cross, a rectangle, and a circle. Each new façade operates as the setting for its own distinct cultural program. An example of ‘Think’ Architecture, the sixty foot high 120-ton polyurethane membrane tent rests on a concrete base has helped “facilitate the fashion house's own transformation into a cultural force” [22].

Curated by the Fondazione Prada, the cocoon like ‘alive building’ structure is an art form that has taken different forms depending on the shape—waist down skirts exhibition space, cinema, students exhibition space, and fashion show space. Prada’s ‘key communication platform’, the Transformer is placed in Seoul due to its’ fast-growing pace both in the business and cultural areas [23].

In an interview about the transportable pavilion [16], establishes that ‘the content could be done anyplace, but the real invention is architecture. The architecture is the only work that really defines a new way of doing things.’ The Prada Transformer is an example of ‘Act’ Architecture, one that modifies and enriches, customer lifestyle. Prada and OMA provide experiential shrine space for its users by being cultural producers. Examples of Think and Act Architecture, Prada seeks to maintain brand distinction by creating social and experiential brand environments.

4.3 Volkswagen Brand City

Volkswagen is an automobile manufacturer based in Wolfsburg, Germany. The Company’s communication platform, Autostadt or ‘Car City’ includes visitor and customer attractions like museum, feature pavilions, cinema, car customize stations, to name a few. “The architecture at Wolfsburg strategically aims to convey quality, security, social competence, and environmental awareness” [17].

4.3.1 Volkswagen Autostadt and Relate

According to Schmitt, ‘Relate’ contains aspects from all experiential modules [1]. Spread over close to a mile, various aspects ‘Think’, ‘Sense’, ‘Act’, and ‘Feel’ modules are visible in the Autostadt – an “exhibition of the definitive car classics allows a view into the past; artworks and films stimulate discussion; interactive research stations offer opportunities for experimentation; and exciting productions” [18]. The Autostadt immerses the users at a cognitive, emotional and visceral level.

4.3.2 VW Level Green – ‘Think’ and ‘Sense’

Level Green is an experiential exhibition that breaks down complex concepts of sustainability into tangible processes. By engaging in over twenty five media exhibits spread over ten thousand square feet visitors can learn about the consequences of climate change, the importance of sustainability for the economy and society, mobility concepts for the future and Volkswagen’s specific approaches towards sustainability. Interactive installations invite the users to reflect on their lifestyle and habits and call for answers to questions on sustainability, thus creating a personal connection to the issue. The users are forced to reevaluate Volkswagen and its products by engaging the customers in the elaborative interactive process—an example of ‘Think’ Architecture.

4.3.3 VW ZeitHaus – ‘Feel’

The ZeitHaus or the “Time House” is a museum that traces the history of the car and automobiles by Volkswagen. The car museum is designed in two sections: one designed for the analytical side of the brain, and the other geared to the brain's creative side. With the objective of creating an effective experience about the Brand, the museum signifies the singular importance of the automobiles as the trend-setters of their and enables them to be seen as artworks of technological design. The consumers of Volkswagen’s ‘Feel Good’ brand trace the history to

strengthen and build upon their existing experiences.

4.3.4 VW MobiVersum and Autolab Car Design Studio– ‘Act’

Aimed to affect bodily experiences, lifestyles, and interactions, an example of Act Architecture maybe found in VW’s MobiVersum. With the goal of introducing driving and safety skills to children and young adults, the driving school is an example of VW’s initiative of ‘Act’ Architecture.

“With the CarDesign Interface in the Autostadt, visitors can become designers themselves. Inspiration for their own designs is found on a stroll through the CarDesign Studio” [18]. The car design interface has a strong communal component to it, one that represents the unifying component of ‘Act’ architecture. A communications interface between the company and its users, the Autostadt is the highest level of creating a brand experience through corporate architecture. Based on the module of ‘Relate’ architecture, the Autostadt works on the sole objective of giving its’ customers an unforgettable experience.

Table 2. Application of Schmitt’s Model to the Case Studies

SEM → CASE STUDY ↓	‘SENSE’	‘THINK’	‘ACT’	‘FEEL’	‘RELATE’
APPLE	▪	▪	▪		
PRADA		▪	▪		
VW	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪

Table 3: Examples of Application of Schmitt’s Model to Case Studies

Spatial Unifiers of Brand Identity → SEM ↓	Brand Store (Apple)	Brand Exhibition (Prada)	Brand City (VW Autostadt)
‘SENSE’	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ User’s Up-Close and tactile encounter with products ▪ Solution Zones ▪ Environment to stimulate the senses ▪ Inviting monumental entrance to underground retail space 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interactive Installations ▪ Media exhibits that involve users
‘THINK’	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Storefront system attract users by surprise, intrigue, provocation ▪ Products act as visual magnets ▪ Stores arranges around people’s lifestyles ▪ Extraneous items like wires are hidden to avoid distraction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ephemeral notion achieved by subverting all preconceived notions of building types ▪ Theatrical stage-like experience ▪ Created more for social events than shopping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exhibits are about pressing issues like sustainability and how VW deals with global issues; thereby influencing users about the brand ▪ Level Green exhibit

Spatial Unifiers of Brand Identity → SEM ↓	Brand Store (Apple)	Brand Exhibition (Prada)	Brand City (VW Autostadt)
‘ACT’	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Alters customers lifestyle; e.g. underground retail space on fifth avenue acts as socializing and networking space ▪ Glass staircase + cube + bridge act transparency and lightness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Museum show on indefinite display ▪ Space for social events ▪ Experiential shrine space for users to act as cultural producers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Car customization studio for users ▪ Driving school on site is a lifestyle change indicator
‘FEEL’			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Museum works as an analytic and a creative tool ▪ Time House Museum to trace the ‘feel good’ brand history
‘RELATE’			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All of the above

5. Conclusions

The application of Schmitt’s model to the three case studies shows that as the consumers are constantly and effectively immersed in brand experiences at a cognitive, behavioral, and visceral level, and as brands compete for consumer attention, the need for a unifying experiential identity is imperative. Corporate Architecture by means of experiential spaces acts as a catalyst for creating a holistic social space centered on user interaction.

The communion between corporate space and experience creates an epicenter effect where the users visit to the brand space and communication about the experience of visiting the space adds a new layer to brand marketing.

Through the case studies, it is visible that Corporate Architecture achieves the goals of Brand Omnipresence, Brand Loyalty, and Brand Reverence.

After the application of Schmitt’s models to Corporate Architecture, it maybe concluded that the model is applicable to corporate spaces. Klingmann applies the model to various examples in architecture, however points out the need for detail when applying the model to transformative spaces [4].

Schmitt’s model works as an analytical tool that helps to identify and explain what experiential modules maybe applied to different operations and functions of corporate Architecture. But the viability of the application of Schmitt’s tool to corporate architecture maybe tested in future studies with empirical tools such as interviews, surveys, and user questionnaires.

Schmitt’s model translates to corporate architecture as an analytical tool, but it will be imperative to understand if it can be applied to the design process as a predictive tool.

Future studies in the field include but may not limited to development of an analytic module system that is directly applicable to architecture.

From the Corporate Architecture standpoint, an ambitious yet important question to ask would be where are companies headed to after ‘Brand Reverence’?

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